

Accessing Work Environment and Teachers Training on Academic Performance of Students in Nasarawa Secondary Schools

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Abstract

This study assessed work environment and teachers training on academic performance of students in Nasarawa secondary schools. The study objectives were to find out the influence of teachers' working environment and training and retaining teachers on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa state public senior secondary schools. Descriptives survey design was employed in the study in gathering data. The instrument of data collection was the Questionnaire on Teacher Motivation and Students' Academic Achievement (QOTMASAA). The study sample consist of 249 teachers and 357 SS2 students from across 26 public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State. The collected data were analysed using frequency count and simple percentages in answering the research questions while chi-square statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that that teachers' working environment and teachers' training played a significant role in academic achievement of students in Nasarawa state. Based on this result, it was therefore recommended among others that teachers should be provided with the right infrastructures, staff quarters/lodge, laboratories, instructional materials/teaching resources and equipped library in other to improve the working conditions in secondary schools.

Keywords: Work environment, Teacher training, Academic performance.

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Introduction

A conducive working environment for teachers has been emphasized as an essential requirement for enhancing students' academic achievement (Gagne, 2007). This is to say that environment for a worker includes a host of structures such as building, furniture, equipment, stationeries, colleagues and the leader. Ortese (2006) maintained that, a teachers' academic achievement in enhancing students' grades in school is influenced by the nature of his work environment this is because, a conducive working environment is free from threat, stress and tension which affects his job performance in the classroom. Similarly, Akpam (2005) asserts that, a pleasant environment with all things being equal provides a conducive working atmosphere for the teachers while a filthy, noisy and dirty environment constitute hindrances to students' academic achievement. Blair (2000) stated that environment of a teacher shapes his development in the sense that it promotes the growth of his certain capabilities and neglect the growth of others.

Blair (2010) noted that inadequate physical facilities in a working environment can lead to undesirable personal behavior of teachers. This is because; large group interaction cannot be conducted without adequate physical space and equipment. He opined that the organizational physical environment should be aesthetically appealing if it will expect the best from her teachers in terms of students' academic achievement. Sogmo (2013) postulated that in order to meet the physical needs of teachers of any organization or institution, a safe structure adequate sanitary facility, a balanced visual environment and appropriate thermal condition and sufficient shelter for work should be provided since the absence of the demoralizes the teacher's towards attaining high students' academic achievement. Udo (2006) stated that a working environment for teachers of any organization should be a controlled one which facilitates an effective working process, while at the same time protecting the physical well-being of the occupants. Similarly, Ortese (2006) explained that the ways in which a teacher's of an organized capability is developed is influenced by the opportunities afforded him by the environment. Ojewole (2014) contended that infrastructural facilities and working tools are essential aids to effective teaching which enhances the performance of students in any school. Argyris (2010) opined that a harmonious working relationship in a working environment of teachers between the organizational management and teachers can positively affect students' academic achievement.

According to Edem (2013) the availability of education opportunities particularly in-service training and study leave enhance workers on their job and makes them to put in their best towards achieving improved students' academic achievement while their absence demoralizes teacher's and renders them ineffective and incapable. Gibson (2007) stated the teacher development can manifest itself in many forms of training evaluations, educational programs and even feedback if executed correctly, the effects of training on

employee performance can often encourage growth within the worker and the organization itself. Dugguh (2004) observed that in-service training improves teachers' skills and boosts their motivation. Jacobs (2007) commenting on the need and importance of teacher's motivation stressed that, the quality and variety of teacher training provided by the principal is the key to motivating them towards students' academic achievement. According to him, teacher training ranges from new time training about your operation to introduce a new concept to a work group by bringing in a computer new system and keeping the teachers motivated about learning new concepts and making the students succeed.

Kpev (2011) stated that the call for opportunities for in-service training, study leave with pay, seminars, workshops and symposia in educational matters and workshops for teachers to update their knowledge about the new method and skills of organization administration will enhance work rate and student academic performance. Ude (2000) observed that, the aim of in-service training of workers in any organization which comes inform of seminar, workshops, conferences which is done in their area of specialization is to make teachers more competent and fully qualified to deliver in these assigned responsibilities. Ada (2010) opined that, training and development of teachers of any school does not only retain the teacher's but motivate them towards better academic achievement of students. According to him, any school that do not give its teachers the opportunity for in-service training, the teachers feel demoralized in putting in their best towards their academic achievement in the classroom. Weirisma (2005) suggested reasons for principals of schools to conduct training among employees which includes; increased job satisfaction and moral among teachers, increased teacher motivation, increased efficiency in processes, resulting in high students' academic achievement. It for this reason that this study seeks to assess work environment and teachers training on academic performance of students in Nasarawa secondary schools.

Theoretical Framework

Walberg Theory of Academic Achievement

Walberg's (1981) "theory of academic achievement is one of the few empirically tested theories of school learning because of extensive review and integration of over 3,000 studies. Using a variety of methods, Walberg identified 28 categories of learning influence among which 8 involved social-emotional influences: classroom management, parental support, student- teacher interactions, social- behavioural attributes, motivational- effective attributes, the peer group, school culture, and classroom climate. Distant background influences (e.g., state, district, or school policies, organizational characteristics, curriculum, and instruction) were less influential on academic performance." The Walberg theory of academic achievement is relevant to the study because it would assist in understanding the reasons why certain learners attain low academic achievement. When related to the study, teacher motivation plays vital role in

determining student academic achievement. The theory is relevant because it establishes the fact that the level of trait teacher will affect a learners' achievement positively or negatively. For instance, if teachers are well motivated, there is the likelihood that student academic achievement will be enhanced.

Research Objectives

The study is aimed at investigating promotion, remuneration and teachers' productivity: evidence from Nasarawa state. Specifically, the study intends to:

The study specifically intends to:

1. Find out the influence of teachers' working environment on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa state public senior secondary schools.
2. Determine the influence of training and retraining of teachers on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa state public senior secondary schools.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the influence of teachers' working environment on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools?
2. What is the influence of teachers' training and retraining on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools?

Research Hypothesis

The following hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: Teachers' working environment as no significant influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.

HO₂: Training and retraining of teachers has no significant influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.

Research method

The descriptive survey design was adopted in this study. This choice of this is due to the fact that the study involves collection of data from a representative sample of the population within a short period of time. A total of 249 teachers and 357 SS2 students were selected for the study. The technique of cluster sampling

was used to draw the sample for the study. In this process, each local government area of the state was treated as clusters, using simple random sampling. In the process five local government areas were drawn by balloting with replacement. Additionally, 26 schools were selected across the five selected local government areas using simple random sampling. In all, 26 schools 249 teachers and 357 SS2 students were selected for the study. The Questionnaire on Teacher Motivation and Students' Academic Achievement (QOTMASAA) was used in collecting data for the study. The collected data were analysed using frequency count and simple percentages in answering the research questions while chi-square statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Questions 1: What is the influence of teachers' working environment on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools?

Table 1. Frequency Counts, Mean and Standard Deviation on Respondents Ratings on the Influence of Teachers' Working Environment among Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Teachers' Working Environment	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D	Remark
The classrooms in the school are comfortable for learning and this enhances students' academic performance.	60	44	46	99	2.74	1.22	Accepted
Inadequacy of chairs in the classroom discourages effective teaching leading to a decline in students' academic performance.	53	60	26	110	2.78	1.22	Accepted
The sanitary condition in the school encourages instructional delivery and this enhances students' performance.	90	47	44	68	2.36	1.22	Accepted
The books in the school library are inadequate for effective teaching that can enhance students' performance.	39	45	58	107	2.94	1.11	Accepted

I use visual and audio-visual devices for teaching and this enhances students' academic performance.	74	39	45	91	2.61	1.25	Accepted
There is adequate furniture in the staffroom and this improves effective teaching which enhances students' academic performance	70	25	52	102	2.75	1.26	Accepted
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviations					2.70	1.21	

Table 1 show that the mean ratings of items on teachers' working environment on students' academic achievement. The mean ratings are of items 1, 2, 4, 5, and 6 are above the cut-off point of 2.50, indicating that teachers accepted these items. This means that the respondents agreed that teachers' working environment influences the academic achievement of students' in Nasarawa state.

Research Questions 2: What is the influence of teachers' training and retraining on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools?

Table 2. Frequency Counts, Mean and Standard Deviation on Respondents Ratings on the Influence of Teachers' Salaries among Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Teachers' Training	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D	Remark
I am trained in the basic teaching skills required for effective teaching and this enhances students' academic performance.	80	31	38	100	2.63	1.30	Accepted
Standard canteen and relaxation spot exist for staff relaxation which promotes services delivery and enhances students' performance.	71	37	24	117	2.75	1.31	Accepted
Teachers in the school are allowed to proceed in-service trainings that improve teaching skills and this enhances students' performance.	30	14	55	150	3.31	1.03	Accepted
The school organizes workshops and seminars which provides me with teaching skills for improving students' performance.	37	22	45	145	3.20	1.11	Accepted

I attend workshops and seminars funded by the government and this improves the teaching skills required for enhancing students' performance.	47	37	47	118	2.95	1.18	Accepted
I have not attended training programmes in the last five years and this restricts the knowledge base required for improving students' performance	57	39	52	101	2.79	1.20	Accepted
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviations					2.94	1.19	

Table 2 show that the mean ratings of items on teachers' training on students' academic achievement. The mean ratings of the six (6) items are above the cut-off point of 2.50, indicating that teachers training enhances the academic achievement of students' in Nasarawa state.

Testing of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Hypothesis 1 (HO₁): Teachers' working environment as no significant influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.

Table 3. Chi-Square Statistics on the Influence of Teachers' Working Environment on Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Variables	\bar{X}	Std.D	df	Alpha (α)	χ^2 cal	p-value	Decision
Teachers' WE*	16.17	3.13	248	0.05	462.63	.008	Reject H ₀₃
Academic Ach.	60.49	5.71					

Level of significance $\alpha < 0.05$ shows a significant influence; WE = Working Environment

Table 3 above shows the Chi-square test statistics (χ^2) on the influence of teachers' working environment on academic achievement of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. The result reveals that there is a significant influence of teachers' working environment on academic achievement of secondary school students given at; [N = 249, $\chi^2 = 462.63$, $p < .05$]. The formulated hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 2 (HO₂): Training and retraining of teachers has no significant influence on students' academic achievement in Nasarawa State public senior secondary schools.

Table 4. Chi-Square Statistics on the Influence of Training of Teachers on Academic

Achievement of Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State

Variables	\bar{X}	Std.D	df	Alpha (α)	χ^2 cal	p-value	Decision
Teachers' Training*	17.63	3.55	248	0.05	517.60	.000	Reject
Academic Ach.	60.49	5.71					H0 ₄

Level of significance $\alpha < 0.05$ shows a significant influence; t

Table 4 above shows the Chi-square test statistics (χ^2) on the influence of teachers training on academic achievement of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. The result reveals that there is a significant influence of teachers training on academic achievement of secondary school students given at; [N = 249, $\chi^2 = 517.60$, $p < .05$]. The formulated hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the study on hypothesis one show that there is a significant influence of teachers' working environment on academic achievement of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. These results are in line with Uwannah et al. (2019) which revealed a significant and positive relationships among work environment, compensation, and teachers' productivity with the strongest relationship being between work environment and compensation followed by compensation and teachers' productivity and lastly by work environment and teachers' productivity. Babagana and Babagana (2015) findings revealed that, fringe benefits and staff nature of working conditions greatly affected performance of students of Ramat polytechnic, Maiduguri. Result of hypothesis two reveals that there is a significant influence of teachers training on academic achievement of secondary school students in Nasarawa State. This aligns with Oni et al. (2017) results which showed that there is a significant relationship between the motivation of teachers and their productivity; while management style has a significant influence on teachers' motivation and their productivity; there is also a significant influence of teachers' motivation on students' academic performance. Findings of this study is in line with Rahman et al. (2011) results which indicated that there is a significant co-relation between teachers training and student test result. Further in line with the findings of this study is Essien et al. (2016) who found that there exists positive and small relationship between the frequencies of teachers' attendance at workshops on students' academic achievement in social studies.

Conclusion

The study concludes that teachers' working environment and teachers' training played a significant role in academic achievement of students in Nasarawa state. Based on this result, it was therefore recommended among others that in order to improve the working conditions in secondary schools, teachers should be provided with the right infrastructures, staff quarters/lodge, laboratories, instructional materials/teaching

resources and equipped library. This will enable them to have confidence in their job and work hard to ensure high job delivery. Furthermore, teachers should be provided opportunities for professional development. In-service training should be organized for teachers to boost and increase their efficiency and effectiveness. This will also make them to know the new methods of teaching their subjects.

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